

Disentangling electric field effect on spin waves in ferromagnetic insulators

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ABSTRACT

In this paper we extend the micromagnetic theory of magnetostatic surface waves in insulating ferromagnetic thin films to include the effects of an applied electric field. We start by identifying the two main effects on the dispersion relation: the first one is of relativistic nature and emerges as a consequence of the Ahronov-Casher effect, while the second one is a consequence of the electric field induced symmetry breaking operating at the level of magnetic exchange interactions. We support our theory by comparing its predictions with experimental data on yttrium iron garnet thin films taken from the literature. The main result is to evidence the limitations of using the same value of the applied electric field to address both effects and to emphasize how the induced electric polarization of the material plays a major role to determine the amplitude of the two effects both at the level of a local crystal field and at the level of magnetic exchange.

1. Introduction

The effect of electric field on the magnetization of ferromagnets is currently an active topic of research because of the significant implications for future magnetic memory devices [1, 2, 3, 4]. It has been shown that through an electric field, it is possible to tune the phase of the magnetostatic spin waves [3] or to induce an additional, voltage-induced, anisotropy in magnetic memory elements [4]. The electric-field control of spin waves has been exploited in multiferroics [1] to design novel magnonics architectures and in insulating ferromagnets as a method to perform logic operations [2]. The microscopic origin of the electric field effect on ferromagnets has been discussed by several authors. Cao et al. [5] have evidenced the role of an electric field in the acquisition of an additional phase of the spin waves in analogy with the Aharonov-Casher effect [6]. Mills and Dzyaloshinskii [7] have demonstrated that, through the flexoelectric interaction, the electric field has an effect similar to the Dzyaloshinskii Moryia interaction (DMI) leading to an extra term in the dispersion relation which is linear in the wavenumber [8]. Indeed experiments shows that the phase acquired by the spin wave has two components: one is frequency independent and the other is approximately linear with the frequency [3]. The assessment of the interplay of these two effects is therefore crucial to disentangle their relative strength and to arrive to a clear understanding of the electric field effects on the magnetization.

In this paper we investigate the electric field effect in the context of micromagnetics. Our aim is to introduce the two mentioned electric field effects within the continuous description of the magnetization vector in which all the dynamic effects, as for example the spin waves, the domain wall motion and so on, can be properly described. By focusing

on ferromagnetic insulators, the effect of the electric field on the magnetization vector of the ferromagnet is twofold. The first effect [5, 9], sometimes called the magneto electric effect, is of relativistic origin and is due energy associated to the transport of a magnetic moment in an electric field. The associated energy can be written as the product of the magnetic moment current density tensor \mathbf{j}_M and of the electric field \mathbf{E} with a coefficient $1/c^2$ where c is the speed of light. The magnetoelectric effect on the spinwaves gives an additional phase or, equivalently, the dispersion relation results to be shifted of the quantity $(\gamma_e/c^2)E$ where γ_e is the gyromagnetic ratio [9]. Microscopically the magnetoelectric effect has to be associated to the average local crystal electric field felt by the magnetic moments at their atomic lattice sites. The second effect, sometimes called the electric field induced DMI, is associated to the energy terms emerging from the broken inversion symmetry caused by the electric polarization of the magnetic crystal [7]. Within micromagnetics, the appropriate approach to this second effect is a gauge theory applied to the exchange energy term of ferromagnetism [10, 11]. The result of the gauge approach is to provide two additional terms to the micromagnetic energy: i) a DMI type energy term, with coefficient D (proportional to the electric field) plus ii) an hard axis anisotropy along the direction of the electric field with coefficient D^2 [12]. Microscopically, this second effect is due to the local crystal electric field felt while transmitting the exchange interaction between spins [11]. Both effects modify the dispersion relation of the spin waves, albeit in qualitatively different ways. Even if the spin wave dispersion relations with DMI are well known [8], in order to describe the spin waves in ferromagnetic insulators under electric field we have to also consider the magnetoelectric relativistic shift and the additional anisotropy obtained from the DMI-type gauge theory. In this paper we extend the existing formalism with these two additional terms in the case of magnetostatic Damon-Eshbach surface waves [13, 14, 15, 16] in which one

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has a thin film with thickness d along x , main applied field and main magnetization direction along z and propagation direction of the spin waves along y . We additionally consider the role played by the metallic electrodes, needed in the experiments, as boundary conditions for the magnetostatic field. The results are compared with the experimental data of the magnetic field and electric field dependence of the phase acquired by magnetostatic spin waves on ittrium iron garnet $\text{Y}_3\text{Fe}_5\text{O}_{12}$ (YIG) thin films from Ref.[3].

Figure 1: Electric field effect on a particle with magnetic moment μ and velocity v (left) and on a spin waves with main magnetization vector along z , transported magnetic moment in the opposite direction and group velocity v_g along y (right). The component of the electric field giving an effect is the one along x .

2. Electromagnetic momentum of spin waves

The presence of an electric field \mathbf{E} on a particle in motion with velocity \mathbf{v} and with a magnetic moment μ has the effect to change the canonical momentum. In addition to the kinetic momentum one finds the electromagnetic momentum given by $-(1/c^2)\mathbf{E} \times \mu$ (see Fig.1 left). The consequence of the presence of the electromagnetic momentum is the acquisition of an additional phase when the particle traverses a region with an electric field. This effect is dual to the celebrated Ahronov-Bohm effect for charged particles and is know as the Aharonov-Casher effect [6]. Since spin waves have a finite group velocity and transport a net magnetic moment, when they propagate in an electric field they will also acquire an additional phase. To see this effect starting from the classical micromagnetic framework one has to write the Lagrangian corresponding to the precession equation and add the energy term describing the interaction between the electric field and the magnetic moment current, $-(1/c^2)\epsilon_{ijk}E_k j_{M,ij}$, where ϵ_{ijk} is the Levi-Civita tensor. From the complete Lagrangian it is not straightforward to write down the equation of motion because the expression of the magnetic moment current density is not explicit. However by limiting to the case of linear spin waves, one can show that the Lagrangian with the electric field can be expressed as the classical one provided one redefines the derivative operator [9]. For the spin waves dispersion relation, this corresponds to redefine the wavenumber. We choose the main magnetization vector along z (with a magnetic field along z , H_z), the propagation direction along y and the electric field along x (see Fig.1 right) and we get that any dispersion relation will be shifted in the wavenumber as

$$q_y \rightarrow q_y + (\gamma_e/c^2)E_x \quad (1)$$

The shift will apply to all kind of spin waves including magnetostatic waves. Of interest here are the surface waves with dispersion relation

$$\frac{\omega}{\mu_0\gamma_e M_s} = \sqrt{H_0^2 + \frac{M_s^2}{4} [1 - \exp(-2d|q_y|)]} \quad (2)$$

where M_s is the saturation magnetization,

$$H_0 = \sqrt{H_z(H_z + M_s)} \quad (3)$$

and d is the thickness [16]. Fig. 2 shows the sketch of the dispersion relation with the electric field shift. With small wavenumbers, the dispersion relation is approximated as a linear relation and by including the electric field shift we get

$$\frac{\omega}{\mu_0\gamma_e M_s} \simeq \frac{H_0}{M_s} + \frac{M_s d}{4H_0} |q_y + (\gamma_e/c^2)E_x| \quad (4)$$

Microscopically, this effect is due to the average crystal field felt by the magnetic moments at the crystal sites. In centrosymmetric crystals like YIG we expect that the average crystal field will be of the same order of the applied electric field. With the constant $\gamma_e/c^2 \simeq 1.95 \cdot 10^{-6}$ V and an applied electric field $E_x = 10^6$ V/m, we get a wavenumber shift of about 1.95 m^{-1} , corresponding to a small but measurable effect.

Figure 2: Effect of the electromagnetic momentum on spin waves. The picture shows the sketch of the dispersion relation for magnetostatic surface waves without (dashed gray line) and with (full red line) electric field (Eq.(4))

3. Electric field induced DMI

Considering the exchange interaction of ferromagnets, the presence of an electric field can induce DMI-type effects [7]. To treat the electric field induced DMI we use a macroscopic approach in which we change the definition of the derivative by including the effect of a gauge field [17]. To formulate the gauge theory of DMI we follow the approach of Refs.[10, 11] and we promote the global $\text{SO}(3)$ symmetry to a local $\text{SO}(3)$ symmetry. The procedure is as

follow. One has first to look for the global transformations which leave the Lagrangian invariant. For ferromagnets, these transformations are the rotations of the magnetization vector. Second, one has to introduce the corresponding local transformations and ensure the invariance under them (called gauge invariance) by introducing a covariant derivative dependent on the gauge field. By substituting the normal derivatives with the covariant ones the Lagrangian becomes invariant under local transformations but the corresponding gauge field is included in the physical description. In the case of ferromagnetism described by a continuous magnetization vector the covariant derivative D_i is defined as

$$D_i m_k = \partial_i m_k + \epsilon_{ljk} m_j D_{il} \quad (5)$$

where ∂_i is the usual derivative, m_k is the normalized magnetization and D_{il} is the gauge field. If we take only the antisymmetric part $D_{ij} = \epsilon_{ijl} D_l$ of the gauge field and choose it along x , D_x , we find that the exchange energy of micromagnetism will be proportional to

$$(\mathbf{Dm})^2 = (\nabla \mathbf{m})^2 - 2D_x(m_x \partial_y m_y - m_y \partial_y m_x) + 2D_x(m_z \partial_z m_x - m_x \partial_z m_z) + D_x^2 m_x^2 \quad (6)$$

where, at the right hand side we get: i) the usual exchange, ii) the DMI-type energy term and iii) an hard x axis anisotropy term [12]. The gauge field D_x , in unit m^{-1} , quantifies the strength of the DMI effect. The spin wave dispersion relation for surface waves with DMI and x axis anisotropy, always in the approximation of small $|q_y|$, is

$$\frac{\omega}{\mu_0 \gamma_e M_s} \simeq \frac{H_0}{M_s} + \frac{M_s - H_{AN}}{4H_0} |q_y| d + 2l_{EX}^2 D_x q_y \quad (7)$$

where we find at the right hand side a term linear in the wave vector q_y as obtained in Ref.[8], but we also get the effect of the anisotropy along x , $H_{AN} = -M_s(l_{EX} D_x)^2$ where $l_{EX} = 2A/(\mu_0 M_s^2)$ is exchange length and A is the exchange stiffness. The field H_0 is now $H_0 = \sqrt{H_z(H_z + M_s - H_{AN})}$. The main effect of the DMI-type energy terms is to change the group velocity of the spin-waves by $\Delta v_g = \mu_0 \gamma_e M_s 2l_{EX}^2 D_x$. From crystal symmetry considerations we expect that, for a centrosymmetric crystal like YIG, the DMI effect is negligible without an applied electric field [11]. Microscopically, the gauge field must be related to the local crystal electric field, therefore we identify $D_x = (\gamma_e/c^2) E_x$. Fig. 3 shows the sketch of the dispersion relation with the change of the slope due to the electric field. An open point is however which is the electric field to be used in the DMI-type effect. The applied electric field is able to polarizes the crystal and to modify the average value of the local crystal field felt while transmitting the exchange interaction between spins. The average local crystal field will be proportional to the applied electric field E_x however the order of magnitude can be much larger. As a very rough

estimate we can possibly expect values for the crystal field as large as 10^{12} V/m, then we can expect $D_x \sim 10^6 \text{ m}^{-1}$. With these values, in YIG with $\mu_0 M_s \simeq 0.18$ T, $A \simeq 0.4 \cdot 10^{-11}$ J/m and $l_{EX} \simeq 18$ nm we expect $\Delta v_g \sim 20$ m/s.

Figure 3: Effect of the electric field induced DMI. The picture shows the sketch of the dispersion relation for magnetostatic surface waves without (dashed gray line) and with (full red line) electric field (Eq.(7))

4. Magnetostatic waves with metallic boundaries

The application of an electric field along x requires the presence of metallic electrodes that also act as metallic boundary conditions for the magnetostatic field. The effect of metallic boundaries on surface waves has been studied by Bongianini [18], Yukawa [19], and O’Keeffe and Patterson [20]. If we also include the presence of an anisotropy along x we find the local inverse susceptibility matrix given by

$$\bar{\chi}^{-1} = \frac{1}{M_s} \begin{bmatrix} H_z - H_{AN} & i\omega/(\mu_0 \gamma_e) \\ -i\omega/(\mu_0 \gamma_e) & H_z \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

By inverting the matrix we write the susceptibility as

$$\bar{\chi} = \begin{bmatrix} \chi_x & -i\kappa \\ i\kappa & \chi_y \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

and we find the dispersion relation by solving the equation

$$[\mu^2 - \kappa^2 + t_+ t_- - \nu \kappa (t_+ - t_-)] t_d + \mu (t_+ + t_-) = 0 \quad (10)$$

where $\mu = \sqrt{(1 + \chi_x)(1 + \chi_y)}$, $\nu = \pm 1$ is the traveling direction, $t_d = \tanh(d|q_y|)$, $t_{\pm} = \tanh(g_{\pm}|q_y|)$ and g_{\pm} are the air gaps between the ferromagnet and the electrodes. Fig.4 shows as an example the dispersion relation of YIG with $\mu_0 M_s = 0.181$ T, $d = 5 \mu\text{m}$, $\mu_0 H_z = 60.1$ mT. The electrodes are at $g_- = 0.5$ mm and $g_+ = 34 \mu\text{m}$. The chosen values correspond to the experiments of Ref.[3]. We can see that the presence of the electrodes strongly increases the group velocity v_g for waves traveling in the positive direction ($\nu = 1$) going from $v_g \simeq 0.52 \cdot 10^5$ m/s for the free case to $v_g \simeq 1.35 \cdot 10^5$ m/s for the metallic electrodes case.

Figure 4: Dispersion relation of surface waves for a YIG film of thickness $d = 5 \mu\text{m}$. Points: experimental data from Ref.[3]. Black crosses: free propagation (the original data is shifted by the offset $\Delta q_y = 3800 \text{ m}^{-1}$); red squares: metallic electrodes. Lines: theory from the solution of Eq.(10). Black line: free propagation; red line metallic electrodes. The curves are obtained with the following parameters: $\mu_0 M_s = 0.181 \text{ T}$, $\mu_0 H_z = 60.1 \text{ mT}$, $g_- = 0.5 \text{ mm}$ and $g_+ = 34 \mu\text{m}$. The purple line is a linear fit of the solution with metallic electrodes.

5. Comparison with experimental data

The experiments of Ref.[3] were performed on a YIG single crystal of thickness of $5 \mu\text{m}$ grown on gadolinium gallium garnet (GGG) substrate. The dispersion relation was measured by placing two RF antennae at a distance of 30 mm and by measuring the phase $\Delta\varphi$ acquired by the spinwave from the transmitting to the receiving antenna. The electric field was applied by adding electrodes in the central part of the YIG waveguide as shown in Fig.5. The presence of the metallic electrodes changes the dispersion relation as shown in Fig.4 where the points are the measured data from Ref.[3]. The fit of the data in the free case (without electrodes) was obtained by adding an offset to the data of $\Delta q_y = 3800 \text{ m}^{-1}$ due to the fact that the experimental method does not permit to address the starting point of the dispersion relation. When the electric field was applied, the acquired phase $\Delta\varphi$ displayed a small change linear with E_x . As $\Delta\varphi = -L_y \Delta q_y$ where $L_y = 20 \text{ mm}$ is the length of the electrodes, we can derive the electric field induced change in the wavenumber $\partial q_y / \partial E_x$ as a function of the exciting ω . The experimental data shows that $\partial q_y / \partial E_x$ has two contribution: one frequency independent at ω_0 and one frequency dependent proportional to $(\omega - \omega_0)$ where ω_0 is the resonance of the uniform mode. The first one can be attributed to the magnetoelectric effect while the second to the electric field induced DMI.

The comparison of Eqs.(4) and (7) with experimental data immediately highlights an important point: if we were to use the value for the applied electric field to get the experimentally obtained dispersion relations we would end up by overestimating the relativistic correction and by greatly underestimating the DMI-like contribution. As anticipated

in sections 2 and 3, the very nature of the electric field appearing in the dispersion relation needs careful consideration. Therefore we let the electric field appearing in Eqs.(4) and (7) as a fitting parameter and determine the two different values at the applied electric field of 10^6 V/m . The determination of the two parameters is straightforward. The experimental value of the frequency independent change is, at applied electric field of 10^6 V/m , $\Delta q_y(\omega_0) = 2.5 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ m}^{-1}$. By using Eq.(4) this values corresponds to $E_x \simeq 1.2 \cdot 10^4 \text{ V/m}$. The measured frequency dependent change is

$$\frac{\partial \Delta q_y}{\partial \omega} = \Delta \left(\frac{1}{v_g} \right) = 3.2 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ s/m} \quad (11)$$

By approximating Eq.(7) as $\omega \simeq \omega_0 + v_{g,0} |q_y| + \Delta v_g q_y$ we get $E_x \simeq 10^{10} \text{ V/m}$. With these values of the parameters the effect of the anisotropy $(I_{EX} D_x)^2 / M_s$ is of the order 10^{-7} and can be disregarded.

Figure 5: Sketch of the YIG waveguide of Ref.[3]. The YIG single crystal (green) has thickness of $5 \mu\text{m}$. Spinwaves are measured by two RF antennae (blue) at a distance of 30 mm . The electric field is applied by means of electrodes (red) of length 20 mm . The front electrode is almost in contact with the YIG (the resulting gap from the fit is $34 \mu\text{m}$) the back electrode is in contact with the GGG substrate (not shown) and the resulting gap is 0.5 mm .

6. Discussion and conclusions

The main result of the inclusion of the electric field in the dispersion relation of the magnetostatic spin waves is given by Eqs.(4) and (7). The comparison with experimental data on YIG of Ref.[3] however highlights that we cannot employ the value of the applied electric field to get the experimentally obtained dispersion relations without a slight overestimation of the relativistic correction and great underestimation of the DMI-like contribution. Therefore by letting the electric field in Eqs.(4) and (7) as a fitting parameter we get two different values for an applied electric field of 10^6 V/m . We discover that the electric field of Eq.(4) can

be interpreted as an effective electric field perceived by the traveling spin wave with order of magnitude $\sim 10^4$ V/m while the electric field necessary to reproduce the required tilt as a consequence of the effect on magnetic exchange, Eq.(7), must have order of magnitude of $\sim 10^{10}$ V/m. To address this difference, we recall how according to the discussion in sections 2 and 3, the very nature of the electric field appearing in the dispersion relation needs careful consideration. In the case of the magneto electric coupling, we are dealing with something closer to the applied electric field, perhaps mediated by some partial screening of the material. In the case of the electric field in the modified version of magnetic exchange, the relevant electric field has to come from the crystal electric field. Of course, in the absence of an applied electric field, the centrosymmetry of YIG forbids any form of DMI like exchange.

In conclusion, we have shown that through a theoretical analysis of the electric field effect on the dispersion relation of magnetostatic surface waves, two main contributions emerge: a purely macroscopic relativistic one and a contribution that operates on the level of quantum mechanical magnetic exchange. We speculate that since the physical origin of these two is drastically different, the nature of the electric field itself must be carefully considered when analyzing experimental data: in the case of the magnetoelectric relativistic contribution, an effective electric field of an order of magnitude similar to the applied electric field can be considered. For the contribution operating on the level of magnetic exchange, a much stronger electric field must be considered whose origin lies in the external field induced electric polarization of the material.

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